

A New Home for Scholarly Communication? Shedding Light on the Academic #TwitterMigration

André Bittermann*

Leibniz Institute for Psychology (ZPID), Germany | abi@leibniz-psychology.org

Tim Lauer*

Leibniz Institute for Psychology (ZPID), Germany | tl@leibniz-psychology.org

Fritz Peters

Leibniz Institute for Psychology (ZPID), Germany | frpe@leibniz-psychology.org

*shared first authorship

ABSTRACT

After the acquisition of Twitter by Elon Musk in 2022, many academics called for leaving Twitter and using alternative platforms such as Mastodon. Applying social impact theory, we hypothesize that academics on Twitter are more likely to migrate to Mastodon if they are under high social influence from #TwitterMigration influencers in their academic social network. We also hypothesize that researchers who endorse the open science movement are more likely to migrate to Mastodon than researchers who do not. We use an available dataset of nearly 500,000 researchers on Twitter and openly available account lists. This research-in-progress aims to determine the persuasive effect of academic influencers on the behavior of the research community, with implications for the dissemination and implementation of scientific practices and reforms.

KEYWORDS

scholarly communication; social media; open science; academic social networks; psychology of science

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, social media has become increasingly important for science communication, both within the professional community and outside in the transfer of knowledge to the general population (e.g., Sugimoto et al., 2017; Zhang & Lu, 2023). Among the various platforms, Twitter is considered the most popular choice by researchers (e.g., Muscanell & Utz, 2017). However, Elon Musk's acquisition of Twitter in October 2022 and the accompanying changes to the platform triggered the so-called #TwitterMigration: Many users, including researchers active in the open science movement, called for leaving Twitter and using alternative platforms (e.g., Nosek, 2022; Schönbrodt, 2022). In particular, the decentralized network Mastodon attracted a lot of attention and saw a sharp increase in user accounts starting in late October 2022 (Nicholas, 2023).

In the light of potential risks associated with highly connected laypeople commenting on scientific issues, there have been growing discussions and calls in recent years for academics to take on the role of influencers and opinion leaders on social media (Mojarad, 2017; Zhang & Lu, 2023). Specifically, the academic #TwitterMigration is an example of a social movement in science that may have been driven by the persuasion processes of academic influencers. Previous work has applied *Social Impact Theory* (Latané, 1981) – a framework to quantify the amount of social impact an individual experiences in a social setting – to examine persuasive processes in Twitter networks (e.g., Lin et al., 2019). In the context of social media, the term *influencer* has previously been defined as an individual who exerts great influence over other users and shows the ability to influence their opinion and behavior (More & Lingam, 2016). Moreover, influencers contribute to how information flows and impact its dissemination (Bakshy et al., 2011; Lin et al., 2019). The purpose of our research is to investigate the persuasive effect these *academic* influencers have on migration behavior, with broader implications for how scientific practices and reforms are spread and put into practice within the research community. In addition, as several properties of the platform Mastodon (e.g., free open-source software, content stream not modified) are in line with the goals of OpenScience, Open Science endorsement may affect migration behavior too.

HYPOTHESES

H1: Researchers who are under higher social influence from #TwitterMigration influencers are more likely to migrate to Mastodon than researchers who are under lower social influence.

H2: Researchers who endorse the open science movement are more likely to migrate to Mastodon than researchers who do not.

METHODS

Data

Researchers' public behavioral traces on Twitter and Mastodon are collected using application programming interfaces (API) of the platforms: Tweets on the topic of #TwitterMigration (using the search terms “TwitterMigration”, “TwitterExit”, “TwitterExodus”, “JoinMastodon”, “MastodonMigration”, “ScienceMastodon”, “AcademicMastodon”, “Mastodon”), as well as profile information of the corresponding users to identify academic

influencers, follower lists of these influencers, profile information of researchers on Twitter identified by Mongeon et al. (2022) and listed on public lists, and timestamps of researchers' tweets and Mastodon posts from November to December 2022 to compare activity on both platforms.

Analytical Procedure

Social Impact

According to Social Impact Theory (Latané, 1981), social impact is the product of three factors: 1) strength, 2) immediacy, and 3) number of sources. We operationalize this as follows: For *Strength* (salience, importance, or intensity of influencing source), we define an influence score metric (Shalaby & Rafea, 2013) with range 0-1 for each person who has actively tweeted on the topic of #TwitterMigration. The score is calculated by the weighted sum of 20% “global” metrics (followers count, listed count) and 80% “local”, topic-specific metrics (number of retweets, likes, and mentions for tweets containing at least one of the keywords). For *Immediacy* (proximity of influencing source), we focus on social proximity in terms of similar interests. Specifically, for each user, we will extract hashtags (excluding hashtags related to #TwitterMigration), and calculate their weighted embeddings based on hashtag frequency (using RoBERTa). Similar profiles are determined by calculating cosine similarity of the users' aggregated embeddings. The *Number of Sources* is the number of #TwitterMigration influencers that the user is following on Twitter, scaled to range 0-1 (min/max). The final product, “Social Impact”, serves as a continuous, z-standardized predictor.

Open Science Endorsement

Users are regarded as endorsing open science if they state “Open Science” or grammatical variants in profile descriptions (without negation), or post on open science with a positive sentiment (in average across their max. top 100 posts). For this, we will use a transformer model fine-tuned for sentiment analysis (i.e., Twitter-roBERTa-base). “Open Science Endorsement” serves as a binary predictor (yes/no).

Migration

To determine if migration has occurred, Twitter profiles are linked to Mastodon profiles. Specifically, this is done on the basis of the public lists and by using the public information on Twitter (e.g. Mastodon account name included in the profile). Of the matched individuals, account activity is determined based on the timestamps of posts on the two platforms. This is used to determine whether - in analogy to migration research - a platform migration in the sense of a "shift of the center of life" has taken place (Treibel, 2008). The dependent variate “Migration” is a factor with two levels (yes/no).

Statistical model

We statistically test whether high social impact and open-science endorsement predict migration from Twitter to Mastodon while taking potential covariates into account. We will use a logistic regression model for both hypotheses:

$$\text{Logit}(P(\text{Migration})) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 * (\text{Social Impact}) + \beta_2 * (\text{Open Science Endorsement}) + \beta_3 * (\text{Follower Count}) + \beta_4 * (\text{Following Count}) + \beta_5 * (\text{Account Age}) + \beta_6 * (\text{Tweet Count}) + \varepsilon$$

EXPECTED RESULTS AND IMPLICATIONS

At the time of writing, the study planning phase has been completed and data collection is partially finished. We aim to present final results at the METSTI workshop. We expect social impact and open science endorsement to be important predictors of migration behavior. Further exploration may reveal members of a certain research field to be more prominent among influencers and migrating users.

Our study aims to expand the understanding of social persuasion processes in scholarly communication, thereby contributing to the field of metascience. Moreover, from a methodological perspective, the study aims to provide initial insights into the possibilities and limitations of such a computational psychology of science. The adjective "computational" is used - in reference to the field of computational social science - to emphasize the use of digital behavioral traces on the Internet and analysis using machine learning and computational natural language processing methods to answer metascientifically relevant questions.

CONCLUSION

Insights from an analysis of these social processes hold the opportunity to support the implementation of academic practices and reforms (e.g., the adaptation of open science practices, use of consistent terminology). Influential researchers who are active in social media could help drive changes that are necessary but that the community itself must sustain (see Smoktunowicz et al., 2020). The case study of #TwitterMigration can help explore initial evidence on the persuasive effect of academic influencers on the behavior of the research community.

REFERENCES

- Bakshy, E., Hofman, J. M., Mason, W. A., & Watts, D. J. (2011). Everyone's an influencer. *Proceedings of the Fourth ACM International Conference on Web Search and Data Mining - WSDM '11*. <https://doi.org/10.1145/1935826.1935845>
- Latané, B. (1981). The psychology of social impact. *American psychologist*, 36(4), 343–356. <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1037/0003-066X.36.4.343>
- Lin, J., Wang, Z., Jin, X., Huang, Y., & Chen, R. (2019). Identifying Opinion Leaders in Twitter during Social Events: Social Impact Theory from Influencer's Perspective. *2019 4th International Conference on Communication and Information Systems (ICCIS)*. <https://doi.org/10.1109/iccis49662.2019.00042>
- Mojarad S. (2017). Social media: More scientists needed. *Science*, 357(6358), 1362–1363. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aap9655>
- Mongeon, P., Bowman, T. D., & Costas, R. (2022). An open dataset of scholars on Twitter (arXiv:2208.11065). *arXiv*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2208.11065>
- More, J. S., & Lingam, C. (2016). A Scalable Data Mining Model for Social Media Influencer Identification. *Communications in Computer and Information Science*, 625–631. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-10-3433-6_75
- Muscanell, N., & Utz, S. (2017). Social networking for scientists: an analysis on how and why academics use ResearchGate. *Online Information Review*, 41(5), 744–759. <https://doi.org/10.1108/OIR-07-2016-0185>
- Nicholas, J. (2023, January 7). Elon Musk drove more than a million people to Mastodon – but many aren't sticking around. *The Guardian*. <https://www.theguardian.com/news/datablog/2023/jan/08/elon-musk-drove-more-than-a-million-people-to-mastodon-but-many-arent-sticking-around>
- Nosek, B. [@BrianNosek]. (2022, October 31). *Even if the Mastodon migration only affects #academictwitter, it could be a great success*. [Tweet]. Twitter. <https://twitter.com/BrianNosek/status/1587024198567952386>
- Schönbrodt, F. [@nicebread303]. (2022, October 31). *My #NovemberMigration pledge* [Tweet]. Twitter. <https://twitter.com/nicebread303/status/1587113778474164225>
- Shalaby, M., & Rafea, A. (2013). Identifying the topic-specific influential users and opinion leaders in twitter. *Acta Press*, 793, 16-24.
- Smoktunowicz, E., Barak, A., Andersson, G., Baños, R. M., Berger, T., Botella, C., Dear, B. F., Donker, T., Ebert, D. S., Hadjistavropoulos, H. D., Hodgins, D. C., Kaldo, V., Mohr, D. C., Nordgreen, T., Powers, M. B., Riper, H., Ritterband, L. M., Rozental, A., Schueller, S. M., . . . Carlbring, P. (2020). Consensus statement on the problem of terminology in psychological interventions using the internet or digital components. *Internet Interventions*, 21, Article 100331. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.invent.2020.100331>
- Sugimoto, C. R., Work, S., Larivière, V., & Haustein, S. (2017). Scholarly use of social media and altmetrics: A review of the literature. *Journal of the association for information science and technology*, 68(9), 2037-2062. <https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.23833>
- Treibel, A. (2008). Migration. In: Baur, N., Korte, H., Löw, M., Schroer, M. (Eds.), *Handbuch Soziologie*. VS Verlag für Sozialwissenschaften. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-531-91974-4_15
- Zhang, A. L., & Lu, H. (2023). Scientists as Influencers: The Role of Source Identity, Self-Disclosure, and Anti-Intellectualism in Science Communication on Social Media. *Social Media + Society*, 9(2), 20563051231180623. <https://doi.org/10.1177/20563051231180623>